

Study of Forest Land Function Transfer and its Role in Labour Absorption, Economic Growth and Increase in Human Development Index in West Kalimantan

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ABSTRACT: Timber forests have many functions and play an essential role in human life. This means that the existence of timber forests provides many benefits for human life. Economic development activities actively implemented throughout the province of West Kalimantan have resulted in more and more areas of timber forest and rubber plantation areas being converted into oil palm plantations. The rampant development of oil palm plantations carried out by investors and those carried out independently by each resident, in essence, provides a significant enough job opportunity for the population in each area that continues to grow. Job opportunities created through economic development offer opportunities to every working population to earn income, fulfilling various life needs is mainly directed to fulfilling family nutritional consumption. If the family's nutrition is guaranteed, then the average life span of the population can be longer. In addition to meeting his family's needs, this income can also be used to finance children's education belonging to the school-age group. If the income earned by each family is large enough, then the family should be able to live in prosperity. This means that timber forest and rubber plantation areas privately owned by the community have been converted into oil palm plantations, significantly contributing to the economic growth of districts/cities in West Kalimantan province and improving the community's welfare.

KEYWORDS: Forest land area, land conversion, economic development, Employment and community welfare

1. INTRODUCTION

Forests are a buffer for the earth which is the source of life for all living things. Ecologists argue that forests are the world's lungs, while water is the energy source for humanity. Every wood root that grows in the forest functions to absorb and carry water into the earth's bowels. Forests are the most sophisticated water circulation machines that any product created by humans cannot replace. Forests cannot be separated from the lives of most Indonesian people because forests provide a source of energy for human beings. Forests produce water and oxygen as elements that are indispensable for human life. Various other forest products also offer benefits to human life. It means Forests have direct benefits that are felt and indirect benefits that humans handle. The benefits of the forest are obtained if the existence of the forest is guaranteed so that it can function optimally. Forest's ecological, economic, and social functions will be fundamental if forest management aligns with conservation efforts to realize sustainable national development.

Forests can provide enormous environmental benefits for human life, including flood mitigation services, minimizing erosion, and water cycle control services. Forest's economic and social aspects will provide a fundamental role if forest management aligns with conservation efforts to realize sustainable national development. Forests can provide enormous environmental benefits for human life, including flood mitigation services, minimizing erosion, and water cycle control services. Forest's economic and social aspects will provide a fundamental role if forest management aligns with conservation efforts to realize sustainable national development. Forests can provide enormous environmental benefits for human life, including flood mitigation services, minimizing erosion, and water cycle control services. Forests have a massive role in the sustainability of human life. Many forests help human life, including forests, play a role in controlling water, forests act as carbon sinks, forests act as providers of water resources, and forests act as providers of various kinds of needs for human life.

The role that forests can give to human life can be seen from forests' functions. Therefore, forest management for the welfare of the community is indeed something that must be taken into account as well as possible by all existing formal institutions, both by the government, the community, the business world, and all components in the community. However, this is often questioned by various parties in the use of land function experts for human life, which method is better to use and how to use it [1]; [2]; [3]; [4] and [5]. The utilization of the economic value of forests to support human life must be carried out in a balanced way with environmental conservation efforts so that woods can be used fairly and sustainably.

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The characteristics of the forest can be seen from the nature of the plurality of land components, biota, and the environment. They all depend on different economic goals. Another peculiarity is the factors necessary for various financial plans that can not always be controlled. Location and time usually have long-term dimensions when they play a prominent role. Differences can be identified from the character and characteristics of the goods and services produced by the forest. Forests can provide human products in various quantities and types for multiple uses. These products vary, from tangible to those that cannot be touched or from those whose benefits are direct (direct products) to indirect products. Tangible products are forest products in processed wood products, such as industrial wood (industrial wood) and non-industrial wood, namely firewood for household use, and other non-timber vegetation such as rattan and pine resin (damar), tengkawang fruit, and water. For non-tangible products in the form of water conservation protection services, overcoming water shortages and flooding, soil conservation, countermeasures against wind erosion and water erosion, carbon sinks, nature tourism recreation, land economic value, beauty, health, and balance of environmental ecosystems.

In the last 20 years, many scientists have added insight into the land transfer to more complex settings [6]. Assuming related to cost [7]; [8]; [9], and generalizations across all factors [10] and capital market [8]; [11]. It combines non-timber values in one criterion [12]. In various parts of the world, forests also allow surrounding communities to carry out agricultural activities. In rural West Kalimantan, people traditionally cultivate rice and multiple vegetables on farmland. This traditional way of farming does indeed give little results and cannot meet the living needs of the farmer's family.

In this regard, [13] suggests that agriculture in developing countries is less efficient with low productivity levels. The results obtained by farmers are still unable to meet their daily needs. In line with [14], this condition indicates that people's lives in rural areas are not yet prosperous; besides that, this can also be exacerbated by other external factors such as the health crisis of the Covid-19 pandemic.

Typical forest characteristics can be seen from the plurality of land components, biota, and the environment. All of them are related to each other and can be used for various economic purposes. Economic goals that cannot always be controlled are a unique characteristic of a forest area, which in the long term will play a very prominent role as location and time develop. West Kalimantan province has a vast forest area. This means this area can develop the agricultural sector, especially oil palm plantations. Concerning agricultural development, [15] suggests that there must be five absolute conditions that must exist and are also supported by five facilitating conditions to accelerate agricultural growth. Similarly, Myrdal [16] states that the farm sector will determine the success or failure of long-term economic development efforts. In connection with that, [16] argue that if a country's economic development is smooth and sustainable, the government must start from rural areas, specifically focused on the agricultural sector. [17] Argues that the contribution of the farming sector to economic development is: providing a more significant food surplus for a growing population, increasing village incomes to be mobilized by the government. According to [18] with sound economic development policies can increase family income and improve community welfare in.

If studied in-depth, development in urban areas is mainly manifested in urban physical development. In the past, the phenomenon of urban development tends to maximize the use of green open space by eliminating the face of nature. Many areas of forest growth land have been converted into residential areas, industrial estate development, recreation area development, and others. For this reason, it is increasingly realized that green buffer areas in urban areas make the city more beautiful and calm. Still, the natural resource environment's sustainability, harmony, and balance will be maintained, providing comfort and freshness. And free the city from air and noise pollution.

In Indonesia, urban development is an activity that is inseparable from a series of national development efforts to realize just and equitable community prosperity, as stated in Pancasila. The development success in one area cannot be separated from the legal basis or the laws and regulations that underlie it or regulate its implementation to achieve goals. The essential reference for the use of urban forests has been implied in the 1945 Constitution, article 33 paragraph (3), which reads: Earth, water, and the natural resources contained therein are controlled by the state and used for the greatest prosperity of the people. Therefore, a sustainable ecosystem must be maintained and continue to function according to human expectations,

In essence, it can be said that forests do function as the principal capital in regional economic development and the national economy; during the Second World War Era (1945–1970), forests were treated as agents for industrialization and development. Economics [19], and the main emphasis remains on the benefits of wood, which continues to grow. The general policies for forestry development in Indonesia as outlined in the five-year development plan of the United Indonesia Cabinet include the following:

- a. Forestry development is directed at providing the most significant benefit to the prosperity of the people while maintaining the preservation and continuity of forest functions, and by prioritizing the conservation of natural resources and environmental processes, maintaining water systems, as well as expanding business opportunities and employment opportunities, increasing sources and income. Foreign exchange countries and spur regional development.
- b. The development of wood and non-timber production is carried out through efforts to increase the exploitation of production forests, community forests, industrial plantation forests, and efforts to increase natural forest productivity supported by the provision of natural forest plant seeds and intense forest cultivation.

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- c. Forests are one of the determinants of ecosystems. Their management is improved in an integrated and environmentally friendly manner to protect and maintain land, water, air, climate, and the environment and maximize the community.
- d. Efforts to rehabilitate forests and critical lands, conserve soil, rehabilitate rivers, lakes, swamps, swamp forests, preserve natural caves, sea corals, rare flora, and fauna, and develop the function of watersheds improved and further refined.
- e. In forestry development, the participation of the community in the surrounding forest area, including the forestry transmigration community, needs to be given opportunities and increased.
- f. The exploitation of forest products is adjusted to the carrying capacity of their natural resources so that the sustainability of forest resources is guaranteed and forest damage can be prevented.
- g. Forestry development needs to be supported by extension activities, education, training, and legislation, provision of information, and research and development.

The general pattern of long-term development is placed in the economic field, which focuses on economic growth that manages Indonesia's natural wealth. In addition, to provide benefits for the present, ensuring the nation's life in the future. Forestry development must be directed to remind the use of forests for domestic industries to generate added value and create as many jobs as possible. In addition, it can also have a positive impact on bilateral relations with neighboring countries such as Malaysia [20]. The function of the forest as part of national development has a close relationship as the principal capital that also lays a strong enough foundation in the take-off process in national economic development.

Economic development experts from all schools believe that economic growth depends on natural resources, power work, accumulation of capital, and technology. This means that one of the factors of production needed in the development process is labor. The availability of labor production factors is intended to drive the development process and enjoy the results of the development that has been implemented. Moreover, the current economic development paradigm defines humans as subjects and objects of action. In line with this paradigm, the goal to be achieved in economic development is to improve the welfare of humanity. According to [16], from the point of view of economics, the result can be interpreted as achieving a sustainable per capita income growth rate to increase output faster than population growth.

With sustainable development, [16] suggest that natural resources in timber forests should be viewed as development assets that need to be preserved. Environmentalists use sustainability to clarify the most desirable balance between economic growth and protecting the environment or natural resources. Regarding the sustainability of natural resources, Development planners must always involve environmental accounting when formulating a policy in large areas and making decisions in areas with small impact [16]; [21]. It was also emphasized that the environment must also be counted as an increasing factor or a reducing factor for economic growth and the level of progress in the welfare of the population in the aggregate. It is time for environmental sustainability to be made one of the main objectives of all development efforts. Therefore it is not the only application.

The idea of sustainability refers to "meeting the needs of the present generation without compromising the needs of future generations." This means that economic growth and the quality of human life in the future are primarily determined by the quality of the environment that humans can maintain at this time. Natural resources owned by a country underlie the life of its entire population. Therefore, the conversion of forest land on a large scale should contribute significantly to economic growth and the human development index in the future. According to Schumacher, the land is a priceless capital. And man must care for and beautify it. Humans' soil management must be directed at four goals: healthy, beautiful, sustainable, and productive. In connection with this sustainability economy, [22] dissertation redefines Schumacher's theory of sustainability economics by prioritizing its economic aspects, as follows:

Economic sustainability is a productive economic activity carried out by humans in utilizing natural resources by using scientific and technological advances that are increasingly efficient and environmentally friendly to achieve optimal production results while maintaining the sustainability and beauty of natural resources for the sustainability of human life fauna and flora. in the future - so that the costs incurred to overcome the problems caused by the damage to these natural resources can be reduced to a minimum

If the existing natural resources are damaged or eroded, then the government and society must try to repair them by increasing the quality and value of these natural resources. One policy strategy that can be implemented to maintain and improve the quality of natural resources is conservation. According to Suparmoko, 2010 conservation is an act of protecting, preserving, and maintaining existing goods. Conservation is the wise use of natural resources that considers time. The idea of maintaining, preserving and preserving natural resources for future use is a non-negotiable necessity. Utilization of natural resources needs to be done efficiently by reducing both economically and socially and maximizing net social benefits over time. The various efforts to conserve natural resources are development strategies that prioritize preserving natural resources. , based on this, this paper wants to analyze how the conversion of forest land functions and its role in labor absorption, economic growth, and the improvement of the human development index in the province of West Kalimantan.

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2. METHOD

The data and arguments built in this paper use qualitative studies, namely by collecting various scientific reference sources and secondary sources through the search for related writings such as the paper on the conversion of forest land and its role in labor absorption, economic growth, and the improvement of the human development index in the province. West Kalimantan

3. RESEARCH RESULT

3.1. Transfer of The Function Of Forest Land And Its Role in The Application of Labor, Economic Growth, and Increasing The Human Development Index in West Kalimantan Province

The Role of Forests in Economic Development

In the 1970s, when the community's basic needs were met through forests, forests had an essential role in the lives of rural communities [23]; [24]. In the general pattern of long-term national development, the focus is on the economic sector, emphasizing economic development that manages Indonesia's natural wealth. In addition to providing benefits for the present, it must also ensure future life. Forestry development must be increasingly directed to remind the use of forests for domestic industries to generate added value and create as many jobs as possible. Optimizing the function of forests and forestry as part of national development has a close relationship as the principal capital that lays a reasonably firm foundation in the take-off process. The general policy of forestry development can be identified as follows:

- a. Forestry development is directed to provide the most significant benefit to the prosperity of the people while maintaining the preservation and continuity of forest functions, and by prioritizing the conservation of natural resources and environmental processes, maintaining water systems, expanding business opportunities and employment opportunities, increasing resources and foreign exchange earnings. Country.
- b. The development of timber and non-timber production is carried out through efforts to increase the exploitation of production forests, community forests, industrial plantation forests, and efforts to increase natural forest productivity supported by the provision of forest plant seeds.
- c. As one of the determinants of ecosystems, forest management must be integrated and refers to environmental insights to maintain and preserve the soil, water, air, climate, and environment and provide the maximum benefit to the community.
- d. Efforts to rehabilitate forests and critical land, soil conservation, rehabilitation of rivers, lakes, swamps, swamp forests, preservation of natural caves, rare flora, and fauna, and the development of watershed functions need to be continuously improved refined.
- e. In forestry development, the participation of the community around the forest area needs to be given opportunities, and the community's role to be increased.
- f. The exploitation of forest products is adjusted to the carrying capacity of their natural resources so that the sustainability of forest resources is guaranteed and forest damage can be prevented.
- g. Forestry development needs to be supported by laws and regulations, extension activities, education and training, provision of information, and research and development.
- h. Various activities have been carried out from 1960 to 2021 to improve environmental functions by rehabilitating critical lands scattered in multiple regions.
- i. The maintenance of nature-loving areas, nature conservation areas, and parts of ecosystems, particularly watershed areas (DAS).

Economic development activities increase regional economic growth, expanding the site's gross regional domestic product (GDP). In connection with this effort to boost economic growth, Jinghan (2008) argues that there are six characteristics of modern economic growth which appear in the analysis based on national products and their components, namely: population growth rate and per capita income, increased labor productivity, high rates of structural change, urbanization flows, expansion of developed countries, as well as flows of goods, capital, and people between nations.

Forest Land Conversion and Community Welfare in West Kalimantan

The function of this vast forest then decreased due to changes in the use of timber forest areas. Since enacting the law on regional autonomy, each new autonomous region is encouraged to explore regional revenue sources by developing economic development. One of the ways the local government is to invite investors who are willing to invest in West Kalimantan Province. The area of timber forest land in districts/cities in West Kalimantan province is decreasing due to the conversion of land functions due to local government policies that permit capital owners (investors) to turn them into oil palm plantations land areas.

The economic sector widely developed in this area is the agricultural sector, especially the oil palm plantation sector. As a result, the vast expanse of timber forest found throughout the province of West Kalimantan (Kalbar) is decreasing in size. This is mainly due to the increasing number of oil palm plantation areas developed in this region. Likewise, the rubber plantation area, which many owners have converted into oil palm plantations, is managed independently (individually).

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According to [16], more than two-thirds of the poorest people in the world live in rural areas. The economic behavior of the rural population is seen as irrational, adopting a subsistence behavior pattern that avoids risk. Todaro and Smith argue that all the problems of living in rural communities begin with the frequent decline in the community's economic life. This shows that the level of community productivity in rural areas is still low and has not been able to meet the needs of farming families. With low productivity, the contribution of rural communities to regional economic growth is also relatively quiet. This condition also illustrates that community welfare in rural areas is still relatively low.

As a result of uncontrolled land conversion, many timber forest areas, including protected forests, have been converted into oil palm plantations. Many have even been abandoned as damaged forest areas and physically no longer exist as forests. The only forest types that still hope to be in good condition are protected forests and conservation forest areas. A conservation forest is a forest area with specific characteristics to preserve biological diversity, consisting of various types of plants, various types of animals, and their ecosystems. A protected forest is a forest that functions as a protection area for life support systems to regulate water use, control erosion, prevent flooding, prevent river water intrusion and maintain soil fertility.

[22], His dissertation concluded that the land conversion in various urban areas in West Kalimantan Province significantly affected economic growth in regions/cities in West Kalimantan Province. This powerful effect is mainly due to the ability of land-use change to increase the added value of the land area that is converted from the agricultural sector to the industrial sector. This high value-added significantly influences regional/city economic growth in West Kalimantan Province. However, [22] also found that the land-use change taking place in regencies/cities in West Kalimantan Province has made a relatively small contribution to the welfare of the people in this area. Ansel's research shows that the small gift of land-use change to the people's interest in this area is caused by the community's unequal distribution of income per capita. The unequal income distribution shows a huge welfare gap between people in this area.

On the one hand, there are groups of people, especially owners of capital, who have very high per capita incomes, but on the other hand, there are groups of people who enjoy very small per capita gains. The unequal income distribution shows a huge welfare gap between people in this area. On the one hand, there are groups of people, especially owners of capital, who have very high per capita incomes. Still, on the other hand, there are groups of people who enjoy very small per capita gains. The unequal income distribution shows a huge welfare gap between people in this area. On the one hand, there are groups of people, especially owners of capital, who have very high per capita incomes. Still, on the other hand, there are groups of people who enjoy very small per capita gains.

In his research, Agus et al. identified the conversion of dry land in the Puncak Region of West Java Province, which was prepared to become an agropolitan center. This land conversion is expected to improve the standard of living of the local community through the development of the agricultural sector. The Puncak area has long been a tourist area and a mountain recreation center, so many agricultural lands in the Puncak area have been converted into housing, hotels, or villas. As a result, the fertile agricultural area is getting narrower. According to Conyers and Hills, regional development requires a development planning model that can ensure a continuous process that includes decisions or choices of various alternative uses of resources to achieve specific goals in the future. Ansel, 2014 concluded that the conversion of agricultural land has resulted in changes in farmer households' social and economic conditions, which shows the decreasing purchasing power of Bandung for various types of goods and services to meet their daily needs. Likewise, Darussalam, in Ansel, 2014 stated that land use had no significant effect on the social welfare of the community. This happens because changes do not follow the shift in land use in the people's interest on Batam Island. The study results by [25] and [22] show that land-use change has no significant effect on community welfare.

One of the reasons that cause changes in forest land use in West Kalimantan Province is to be used as oil palm plantation areas. The choice of investment in the oil palm plantation sub-sector is, of course, in addition to boosting economic growth in the province of West Kalimantan and creating jobs that are wide enough to accommodate the available workforce in this area. Therefore, the development of oil palm plantations is expected to house a relatively large number of workers, which is expected to encourage an increase in the human development index in Indonesia. To increase the rate of economic growth, the available natural resources in the form of timber forests will be exploited on a broader scale for the development needs of the oil palm plantation sub-sector. The exploitation of these natural resources will naturally lead to a decline in the quality of natural resources in the area.

Similarly, [26] show that sawn timber and palm oil exports have a negative trade-off effect on potential deforestation. The increase in sawn timber exports reduces likely deforestation due to imports of logs which are the raw material for sawn timber. Meanwhile, palm oil harms potential deforestation because production in the study area is more for domestic consumption. In a study conducted in five border districts in West Kalimantan Province,

Economic Development and Community Welfare

Economic development, which is being actively implemented, aims to increase regional and national production, which is reflected in GDP/GRDP and is expected to provide various types of goods and services to meet the needs of people's lives in sufficient quantities. Economic development will produce economic growth, seen from the Gross Regional Domestic Product (GDP) increase. This means that at the same time as the economic development process is carried out, during that period, there is also a process of increasing the real gross national product/gross domestic product (GNP/GDP) of a country, which is always higher than conditions

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in the previous period. Of course, an increase in the value of GNP / GDP is expected to increase the income per capita of the population. If economic growth continues to grow at a reasonably high rate, per capita income will also increase proportionally. This means that if economic growth and the level of real per capita income are also higher, the community's welfare should also increase.

Economic growth describes the dynamics of development carried out by each region in various economic sectors. Each part can improve the economic conditions of their respective areas. During the period 2011 to 2016, the economic growth achieved by the districts/cities in the province of West Kalimantan tends to show an increase from year to year. The results of economic development that have been achieved so far have been able to gradually increase the real per capita income of the community. Economic development activities are efforts to reduce poverty, reduce inequality in income distribution among residents, and expand job opportunities. The fact shows that during the period 1960-the 1970s,

The purpose of economic development is to improve the welfare of humanity. According to [27], economic development carried out by a country is initially measured by increasing economic growth and rising real per capita income of the people in that country. Economic growth and a higher real per capita income level should indicate increased welfare. From various research results that have been carried out, it can be seen that the developments achieved in this economic growth have not been able to make a more meaningful contribution in improving the community's welfare. Fatihudin in [22] concluded that economic growth has no significant effect on people's welfare. This means that not every increase in economic growth turns out to have a relatively small contribution to improving people's interests.

Rostow in [17] suggests that economic development in developing countries follows linear growth with five stages of growth, namely:

- a. Set of traditional society (Traditional).
- b. The pre-take-off (Transition) stage.
- c. Take-off stage.
- d. The location of moving towards maturity.
- e. Stage of high mass consumption (High mass consumption).

The division of these stages of growth is intended so that each developing country/region can know its development position based on an evaluation of the development performance in that period. Efforts to carry out economic development in an area aim to increase economic growth, manifested in changes in GRDP. Experts agree that the development process is a deliberate effort to overcome underdevelopment accompanied by efforts to open up the limitations of people's mindsets. This means that the development process must change people's attitudes about all aspects of human life. For example, getting a higher per capita income and life expectancy.

According to [13] the level of success achieved by a country or region in the process of economic development can be seen from the three fundamental values of action, namely: the ability to provide basic needs (life sustenance), they need to be respected (self-esteem), and freedom to choose (freedom to choose). Choice). Economic development activities that are being implemented are expected to increase per capita income according to adequacy standards so that every resident can meet the three basic needs mentioned above: adequate food, shelter, clothing, health, education, and a sense of security. Therefore, the level of success achieved in economic development is the main requirement to improve the community's quality of life.

Amartya Sen [13] states that a person's poor status is determined by function. Development should pay more attention to improving the quality of life and individual freedom. Community welfare can be measured based on the value of the human development index (HDI), with three composite indicators as the level of life as measured by life expectancy, the level of education as measured by years of schooling, the level of fulfillment of basic needs, which is measured by the level of income received by each person. . The HDI value of a country/region shows how far the country/region has achieved the specified targets, namely: life expectancy, primary education for all levels of society, and the level of expenditure for consumption that reflects a decent standard of living. The closer the HDI value of a country/region is to 100, the more the target to be achieved is getting closer. In general, it can be said that the HDI coefficient of West Kalimantan Province in 2019, is 69.74

From various published reports on the HDI of districts/cities in West Kalimantan province, it can be seen that West Kalimantan Province is ranked 28th out of 33 areas in Indonesia. The slow increase in HDI in districts/cities in West Kalimantan Province can be assessed from the achievement of composite indicators that determine HDI, namely education, health, and income per capita. Any changes in these indicators will positively influence human resource development in this area. The still low HDI figure shows that the literacy rate is still low, the average length of schooling is still low, the infant and maternal mortality rate is still high, and the income per capita of the people in the districts/cities in West Kalimantan is still low.

Mangas research (2016) concludes that the variable economic growth significantly affects the Human Development Index in border districts from 2007-2014. The positive value of the regression coefficient indicates a unidirectional relationship. The value of this coefficient illustrates that an increase in economic growth led to the rise in HDI in border districts in West Kalimantan Province. This study concluded that the HDI composite score for the five border districts was on average 61.43. This figure is still far from

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expectations, even though economic development through oil palm plantations in border districts is massive, so further studies are needed.

District/city governments are given the authority to determine regional development strategies and policies with regional autonomy. Considering that this regional autonomy has been going on for two decades, so it is natural that at this time, it is necessary to re-question whether economic development strategies and policies focused on the development of the agricultural sector, especially the plantation sub-sector, is appropriate and make a significant contribution to economic growth and the index. Human development in districts/cities in the province of West Kalimantan.

The Role of Rural Communities in Economic Development

Residents of communities in rural areas essentially have dual functions, namely as producers and as consumers. If examined as a producer, the working population will be part of the production input in increasing the added value of a product or service. This means that wages paid to residents must be taken into account in determining the cost of the product. If the population is studied as a consumer of the agricultural products produced, he will consume various products made. Of course, every product and service that is finished has considered taxes. This tax is a source of regional or state revenue. This means the higher the community's income, the higher the level of consumption. The higher the level of consumption, the greater the regional/state revenue from the tax sector. So it becomes very logical if economists say that the availability of population or human resources (H.R.) in sufficient quantity and quality is one of the development resources.

- a. The population is a development resource.
- b. If population growth is more excellent than economic growth, the population will be a development burden because the food products produced are not sufficient for the community's needs.
- c. Technology is considered unable to keep pace with population growth
- d. According to the law of diminishing returns, income will decrease if the number of workers increases
- e. The population is increasing geometrically, while agricultural products in food are growing arithmetically. As a result, there will always be a widening gap between the people and the provision of food to meet the needs of human life.

In line with the above opinion, Keynes in [17] argues that

- a. The population variable reflects the availability of workers who are ready to work. If the available workforce is not absorbed or does not work (Unemployed), it will impact the high level of poverty (dis-advantage).
- b. Poor people will not be able to save because their marginal propensity to consume (mpc) is close to 1. On the other hand, wealthy people or have high incomes will keep and invest because their mpc is smaller than 1.
- c. The bigger the mpc, the more significant the multiplier effect. This condition will have an impact on the process of increasing job opportunities.

The availability of workforce or human resources in an area is an essential factor determining the success of economic growth, increasing these resources, and using sustainable community technology [28]. Development activities are only a medium. To achieve the goal of improving the quality of human life. The concept of human development places the human individual as the ultimate target of a series of development activities carried out in each country/region. This means that various efforts must be directed explicitly at human development to accelerate economic growth. The level of community welfare is measured by using the Human Development Index (HDI) or Human Development Index (HDI). To determine the level of success in building the quality of human life, it can be seen from the achievement of HDI figures.

The law of diminishing returns can only work if it is assumed that everything else is constant. It should be understood correctly that there are no fixed production inputs such as land, labor, and capital in the long run. This means that these production inputs can decrease or increase depending on human efforts to change them. Based on the previous explanation, it appears that there is a tendency for forest land areas to fall because many have changed functions, The conversion of forest land into oil palm plantations managed by large capital owners and the transformation of privately owned rubber plantation areas into oil palm plantations managed independently by the community is a form of creating jobs for the population. Thus it can be said that the development of oil palm plantations, in addition to playing a role in increasing the country's foreign exchange, is also able to play a role in absorbing labor for a growing population and at the same time encouraging regional development and regional economic growth and the national economy.

The development of oil palm plantations that are rife in this area is a form of job creation. People who work by themselves will get income in the form of wages. The wages are then used to meet various needs of life. This means the greater the number of consumers. The higher the level of wages earned, the higher the individual's ability to meet their needs. The more family members who work, the greater the income earned by the family concerned. On the one hand, an increase in people's income will automatically increase the community's purchasing power, thereby increasing public consumption. On the other hand, if this income is saved in a more significant amount, consumption will decrease. If public consumption decreases, the payment protected (saving) is more influential. The community's ability to mobilize these savings proves that there will be enough funds to invest in various economic activities, including investment in oil palm plantations managed independently by each community. The transformation from a former

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colonial-controlled forest regime to a regime dominated by new pressure group activism has emerged because of freedom of thought, expression, and action in forest management [29].

4. CONCLUSION

As part of a large ecosystem, Forests have many essential functions and roles in supporting living systems. Various great benefits are obtained from the existence of the forest through its position both as a provider of water resources that are very beneficial for human life and the environment. Economic development activities actively implemented in all regions in West Kalimantan Province have resulted in more and more forest areas and rubber plantation areas being converted into oil palm plantation areas. The rampant development of oil palm plantations carried out by investors and those carried out independently by each community, in essence, provides a significant enough job opportunity for the population in each area that continues to grow.

The creation of this job opportunity provides an opportunity for the community to earn an adequate income and demonstrates the community's purchasing power. It can then buy various goods and services its families need. Fulfilling diverse life needs is mainly directed to completing family nutritional consumption. This is intended so that public health remains guaranteed so that the average life span of the population can be longer. In addition to meeting his family's needs, this income can also be used to finance children's education belonging to the school-age group. If the income earned by each family is large enough, then the family should be able to live in prosperity. This means that timber forest areas and rubber plantation areas owned by the community have been converted into oil palm plantations and have contributed significantly to the economic growth of districts/cities in the province of West Kalimantan and community welfare improvement. Various research results in multiple regions show that land-use change improves people's welfare.

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